

Synthesis of novel ZnS@MnFe₂O₄@NaX ternary nanocomposite sonocatalyst for the degradation of methylene blue (MB) organic dye

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Abstract

This work focuses mainly on the degradation reaction of methylene blue (MB) organic dye in the presence of ZnS@MnFe₂O₄@NaX ternary nanocomposite sonocatalyst for the first time. For this purpose, ZnS and MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles were successfully immobilized within the zeolite NaX framework by the hydrothermal method. The as-synthesized ZnS@MnFe₂O₄@NaX zeolite nanocomposite was characterized applying FESEM, EDAX, FTIR, XRD and VSM analyses. Several factors, including irradiation time, initial dye concentration, process type, catalyst dosage, organic dye and type H₂O₂ concentration have been investigated to achieve the maximum sonocatalytic efficiency. In the presence of 150 mg/L of ZnS@MnFe₂O₄@NaX, 25 mg/L of dye, and 4 mM of H₂O₂, the sonocatalytic degradation efficiency attained 98.8% for MB after contact time of 60 min. The hydroxyl radicals (\cdot OHs) were distinguished as the main reactive oxidative species on the degradation of MB under US irradiation. Besides, the reproducibility of the ZnS@MnFe₂O₄@NaX sonocatalyst was studied, which proved that it can be recycled up to five cycles with almost trivial loss of catalytic performance. In addition, the sonodegradation of MB via the ZnS@MnFe₂O₄@NaX zeolite sonocatalyst in the presence of US/H₂O₂ system displays a great performance to evaluate highly treat of organic pollutants from effluents.

Keywords: ZnS@MnFe₂O₄@NaX, Zeolite, Nanocomposite, Methylene blue (MB), Degradation.